

Cyclodextrin-Based and Advanced Nanosponges: A Comprehensive Review on Synthesis, Characterization and Application

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ABSTRACT

Nanosponges are hyper-crosslinked, porous nanoscale carriers that have gained significant attention in pharmaceutical research for their ability to enhance drug solubility, stability, and bioavailability. Among these cyclodextrin-based nanosponges (CD-NS) represent a versatile platform owing to their well-defined inclusion cavities and tunable polymeric networks. Over the past five years, significant progress has been made in developing CD-NS formulations for oral and topical applications. For oral delivery they improve solubility and dissolution of poorly water-soluble drugs, protect labile molecules from degradation and enable sustained release or taste masking in pediatric formulations. Advanced approaches such as ultrasound- and microwave-assisted synthesis, along with hybrid CD-metal-organic frameworks, have further improved loading efficiency, stability, and multifunctionality. Applications span across antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and pediatric formulations, with promising preclinical outcomes. However, challenges related to reproducibility large scale manufacturing regulatory approval and long-term safety remain. The review highlights the synthesis methods, classification, characterization, therapeutic intent, and applications of cyclodextrin-based and advanced nanosponges, characterization, and therapeutic applications, highlighting their strong potential as next generation carriers for oral and topical drug delivery.

Keywords: Cyclodextrin; Nanosponges; Crosslinking Method; Controlled Release; Solubility Enhancement; Bioavailability.

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology has transformed the pharmaceutical and biomedical fields by enabling the design of carrier systems with enhanced solubility, bioavailability and targeted delivery. Among these, nanosponges (NSs) represent a unique class of porous, crosslinked nanoscale carriers that have significant attention in recent years. Nanosponges are three-dimensional, hyper-crosslinked polymeric structures with tunable porosity and large surface area, capable of entrapping a wide variety of guest molecules including hydrophilic, lipophilic and gaseous compound⁽¹⁾

The earliest nanosponges systems were developed by crosslinking cyclodextrins (CDs) cyclic oligosaccharides with hydrophobic cavities and

hydrophilic exteriors using bifunctional or polyfunctional linkers such as carbonyl diimidazole, diphenyl carbonate or pyromellitic dianhydride. This innovation extended the well-established inclusion complexation ability of CDs by providing a rigid, insoluble polymeric network with multiple binding domains and interstitial nanocavities⁽²⁾

Nanosponge research has rapidly expanded beyond cyclodextrin systems to include hyper-crosslinked polymeric nanosponges, inorganic/ metallic nanosponges, and hybrid nanosponges system such as cyclodextrin-metal-organic framework (CD-MOF) composites.⁽³⁾ These innovations have not only enhanced the drug loading and release control properties of nanosponges but also enabled multifunctionally, such as stimuli-responsive

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behavior, catalytic activity, and environmental remediation capabilities⁽¹⁾

The pharmaceutical relevance of nanosponges lies in their ability to improve solubility and dissolution rates of poorly water-soluble drugs, protect labile molecules from degradation and provide sustained and targeted drug delivery. Applications span oral, topical, parenteral and pulmonary routes with several preclinical and clinical studies reporting promising outcomes.⁽⁴⁾ Additionally, environmental applications, such as adsorption of organic pollutants and toxic metals highlight the versatility of nanosponge technology.

Recent literature also emphasizes advanced preparation methods such as ultrasound-assisted and microwave-assisted syntheses which reduce reaction time and improve uniformity and template-assisted or hybrid strategies for precise pore engineering. As the field matures, challenges remain in terms of reproducibility, scale up, regulatory approval, and comprehensive toxicological assessment⁽⁵⁾

Cyclodextrin Based Type of Nanosponge Chemical Structure

Figure 1- α -cyclodextrin nanosponge structure, β -cyclodextrin nanosponge structure, γ -cyclodextrin nanosponge chemical structure

A special enzyme called cyclodextrin glycosyltransferase (CGTase) breaks starch into ring shaped sugar molecules. Cyclodextrin nanosponges are made of a three-dimensional cross-linked polymer network. These are cyclodextrin types are found α , β , and γ . α -cyclodextrin is a cycloamylose composed of six alpha-(1->4) linked D-glucopyranose units $C_{36}H_{60}O_{30}$, β -cyclodextrin is a cyclodextrin composed of seven alpha-(1->4) linked D-glucopyranose units $C_{42}H_{70}O_{35}$, γ -cyclodextrin is a cycloamylose composed of eight alpha-(1->4) linked D-glucopyranose units ($C_{48}H_{80}O_{40}$).

Advantages of Nanosponges⁽¹⁾

- Enhanced solubility and bioavailability:** Encapsulation increases aqueous solubility and dissolution rate leading to improved oral absorption and systemic availability
- Controlled and sustained drug release:** Nanosponges provide zero-order or near-zero order release, avoiding dose dumping.

- Versatility in drug loading:** Can entrap both hydrophilic and lipophilic molecules, including peptides, proteins, and even gases.
- Protection of labile drug:** Encapsulation protects drugs from hydrolysis, oxidation, photodegradation, or enzymatic breakdown
- Reduced toxicity and side effects:** By controlling release and localizing drug action, nanosponges minimize systemic toxicity
- Versatile Routes of NSs:** Suitable for oral, parenteral, topical, pulmonary, and ocular delivery

Disadvantages of Nanosponges⁽¹⁾

- Toxicity concerns:** some crosslinking agents {e.g., diisocyanates, epichlorohydrin} are toxic and residual unreacted linkers may cause cytotoxicity.

- Complex and costly preparation:** Advanced methods {ultrasound-assisted, microwave, or template synthesis} require specialized equipment.
- Regulatory barriers:** No NSs-based drug delivery system has yet received full regulatory approval.
- Limited drug loading capacity:** Although nanosponges are porous the extent of entrapment depends on drug-polymer interactions .
- Stability issues in formulation:** Suspension-based nanosponges formulation may suffer aggregation, sedimentation, or particle growth during storage.
- Unclear long-term safety:** Long-term accumulation, biodistribution and clearance mechanisms are not fully understood.

Figure 2 - The family of nanosponge particle includes carbohydrate-based nanosponge with distinct representations⁽²⁾

Types/ Classification of nanosponges

Nanosponges can be classified according to several criteria. The most basic classification: based on what the sponge is made of:⁽⁶⁾

Table 1 - Material/ core composition

Type	Core materials/ polymers	Examples
Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges (CDNSs)	α, β, γ cyclodextrin crosslinked with linkers like diphenylcarbonate(DPC), carbonyldiimidazole(CDI), epichlorohydrin, diisocyanates, etc...	Strong host-guest inclusion ability; good for both hydrophobic & hydrophilic drug loading. Used widely in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics.

A no of reviews classifies CD-nanosponges in generations, based on additional features beyond just the base polymer⁽⁷⁾

Table 2 - Evolution/Generational classification

Generation	Description	Examples
First Generation (Plain NSs)	Basic CD-based frameworks without special modifications. Includes ether, carbamate, ester, carbonate linkages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ether NSs: CDs crosslinked with epoxide type (epichlorohydrin, diglycidyl ethers) Urethane(carbamate)NSs: Using diisocyanates Carbonate NSs : e.g diphenyl carbonate, CDI Ester NSs: cross-linking with diacid/ ester linker
Second Generation (Modified NSs)	Plain NSs modified to add functional groups(hydrophobic or hydrophilic modifications)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluorescent carbonate or carboxylatedNSs Electrically charged NSs Hydrophobic modified NSs for lipophilic drug loading
Third generation	NSs that respond to external stimuli	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> pH-responsive CDNS

(stimuli-responsive NSs)	(pH, redox. Temp, etc.)to release drug or change behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glutathione(GSH)-responsive NSs • Temperature-responsive NSs • Enzyme-sensitive NSs
Fourth generation (Molecularly imprinted NSs)	NSs which include molecular imprinting to give specificity/selectivity for a particular guest molecule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NSPs imprinted for drugs, toxins or biomarkers: • The polymerization or crosslinking is templated around a molecule so that binding sites are shape for it.

Some literature classifies NSs by what they are meant to do, particularly in advanced systems⁽⁷⁾

Table 3 - Functional/Application-based classification

Category	Features
Stimuli-responsive NSs	Designed to release on trigger: pH change (e.g. tumor microenvironment), redox(higher GSH), temperature, enzyme presence. Help targeted or timed therapy.
Fluorescent NSs	NSs modified with fluorophores for imaging/tracking in vivo or in vitro. Useful in diagnostics or tracking delivery ⁽⁷⁾
Molecular imprinting NSs	As above, polymers shaped to selectively bind certain molecules; useful for sensing cleanup of pollutants or selective drug molecule.
Hybrid NS	Materials hybrids combining organic polymer, inorganic materials or combing multiple functional materials These hybrids may combine drug delivery + imaging or delivery + catalysis etc ⁽⁶⁾

Nanosponges can also be differentiated by their structural arrangement and crystalline properties. Their internal order and packing strongly influence their loading capacity stability and release kinetics⁽⁸⁾.

Table 4 - Physical structure/Crystallinity

Category	Features	Limitation
Crystalline NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better defined cavities and channels • Improved drug inclusions efficiency for certain molecules • Higher mechanical strength and thermal stability 	Sometimes too rigid – slower drug diffusion
Amorphous NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater flexibility of network • Higher swelling and water uptake 	Sometimes lower stability compared to crystalline
Semi crystalline NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balanced rigidity and flexibility • can fine tune release behavior 	Useful in sustained release drug delivery

The crosslinking agent used to prepare NSs play crucial role in determining their chemical stability, hydrophilic-hydrophobic balance, biodegradability and drug binding properties⁽¹⁾

Table 5 - Classifications by crosslinkers

Crosslinkers	Features
Carbonate-Linked NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High stability and porosity • Efficient entrapment of hydrophobic drugs
Ester-Linked NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodegradable, hydrolytically cleavable • Useful for sustained release
Urethane-Linked NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher hydrophobicity • Better for lipophilic drugs

Ether-Linked NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrophilic in nature Suitable for hydrophilic drug encapsulation
Dianhydride/ Mixed-Linked NSs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combination of linkages gives dual properties Can modulate both hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity

Materials Used in Nanosponge Preparation

Table 6 - Materials used in nanosponge preparation

Ingredients	Materials
Cyclodextrin (CDs)	α, β, γ
Crosslinkers	Diphenyl carbonate, carbonyldiimidazole (CDI), Pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA), Diisocyanates, Epichlorohydrin
Synthetic monomers & Polymer	Styrene, divinylbenzene (DVB), methyl methacrylate (MMA)
Solvents	Dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), acetone, ethanol, water, organic solvents
Surfactants	PVA, Tween- 80, Span series

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Direct / Melt Method (solvent -assisted crosslinking)

Dry the chosen cyclodextrin (usually anhydrous β -CD) thoroughly (overnight, 60 - 80°C under vacuum). Combine CD and a carbonate (e.g., diphenyl carbonate, DPC) in a glass flask at a chosen molar ratio 1:4—1:8, depending on desired crosslink. Then heat the mixture under stirring; 90-130°C for several hours often 3-6h to allow carbonate formation (solvent-free). After reaction cool and break the bulk polymer, then wash repeatedly with ethanol to remove phenol and unreacted reagents. Dry (oven or vacuum), then grind and sieve to obtain a powder (further size reduction by ball-milling if nanoscale required)- Purification: Soxhlet or repeated washing with ethanol is typical-check for phenolic residues (from DPC) By HPLC⁽¹⁾

Emulsion/ Solvent-Diffusion:

Prepare an organic phase dissolve polymeric precursor or drug= polymer in a volatile organic solvent (e.g., dichloromethane, ethyl acetate). For polymeric hyper- crosslinked NSs, monomers are dissolved here. Prepare an aqueous phase containing stabilizer (PVA, Tween-80). Add organic into aqueous under high-speed homogenization (or sonication) to create a stable/w emulsion. Initiate polymerization in the droplets (thermal) or allow solvent diffusion/evaporation so the crosslinked NSs particle precipitate. Collect particle by centrifugation, wash, dry (freeze—dry or spray-dry depending on route)- Purification: Centrifuge + wash to remove surfactant; dialysis or multiple water washes to remove residual solvent and surfactant⁽¹⁾

Ultrasound-Assisted synthesis:

Mix CD and crosslinkers often (DPC OR CDI)-often no solvent or minimal solvent. Place the reaction mixture under ultrasonic irradiation (bath or probe sonicator) Typical conditions reported range from temperature up to -90°C with sonication times from 30min to several hours. Cavitation promotes local heating mixing and reaction-Purification: Same as melt-repeated washes: sonochemical routes often permit milder bulk temperature but still require removal of by-products⁽²⁾

Microwave-Assisted synthesis:

Mix anhydrous CD and crosslinkers (e.g., DPC OR CDI) in a microwave-compatible vessel (often solvent-free with minimal solvent). Irradiate under microwave power for short times (10min). Typical power/time combinations depend on instruments and scale; many groups optimize via response surface methods, Cool wash (ethanol/water) dry and grind. Microwave heating gives uniform internal heating and much shorter reaction times versus conventional heating. Purification: Repeated washing or Soxhlet extraction is common⁽⁹⁾

Hybrid NSs: CD-MOF and inorganic hybrids:

Mix cyclodextrin (or CD derivative) with metal salts (Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+}) and organic ligands under solvothermal/ precipitation or room-temperature assembly conditions. The MOF may incorporate CD into pores or the CD may be crosslinked around MOF particles, producing hybrid with high surface area and CD cavities. Isolates wash (to remove uncoordinated ligands/metal salts), dry under controlled conditions. Purifications: Remove leachable metal ions, check for metal-leaching in release media⁽¹⁰⁾

POST-SYNTHESIS DRUG LOADING DRYING/ SIZE- ENGINEERING TECHNIQUES:

A. Common loading routes:

1. **Incubation/ soaking:** Suspend pre-formed NS powder in drug solution (organic or aqueous depending on drug) stir for hours. Solvent removal by evaporation or lyophilization⁽¹⁰⁾
2. **Kneading:** wet mixing CDNS + drug+ small solvent to promote complexation, then dry and mill.
3. **Freeze-drying: (lyophilization):** widely used to entrap labile drugs and produce porous loaded powders⁽¹⁰⁾
4. **Supercritical CO_2 impregnation:** use $scCO_2$ to load hydrophobic drugs without organic solvent residues: attractive green approach⁽¹¹⁾

B. Drying/ Particle engineering:

1. **Nano-spray drying:** : To make inhalable dry powders of nanosponge-drug assemblies⁽¹²⁾
2. **Spray drying:** Gives good control for DPI (dry powder inhaler) formulations: freeze- drying preserves porous structure for sensitive actives.⁽¹³⁾

FACTORS AFFECTING NANOSPONGE SYNTHESIS AND PERFORMANCE:

The successful development of nanosponge depends on several critical formulation and process parameters. These factors not only influence their physicochemical characteristics but also determine

drug loading efficiency, stability, release profile, and therapeutic effectiveness. The major factor is below.

Type of polymer:

The choice of polymer backbone is crucial. Cyclodextrins (α, β, γ -CD), Hyper-crosslinked polyesters, and biodegradable polymers such as polycaprolactone (PCL) or polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) are widely used. Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges provide well-defined inclusions cavities, enhancing solubilization of poorly soluble drugs. synthetic biodegradable polymers (PCL, PLA, PLGA) improve biocompatibility and controlled degradation⁽¹⁴⁾

Type and degree of crosslinking:

Crosslinker chemistry strongly influences nanosponge porosity and stability. Common crosslinkers include diphenyl carbonate (DPC) carbonyl diimidazole (CDI), pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) and epichlorohydrin. Higher crosslinking- small pores, slower drug release. Lower crosslinking- larger pores, faster release but weaker stability⁽¹⁾

Polymer-to-crosslinker ratio:

The ratio directly affects particle size, porosity and encapsulation efficiency. Low ratio- more flexible network, higher swelling. High ratio- dense, rigid structure, but sometimes reduced drug diffusion⁽¹⁾

Solvent system:

The solvent or solvent mixture used during synthesis plays a role in polymer solubility, crosslinking efficiency and particle morphology. Polar aprotic solvents e.g., DMF DMSO promote better dispersion of polymer and crosslinker. Green solvents e.g., ethanol, water are being explored to reduced toxicity⁽¹⁾

Method of preparation:

The preparation technique (solvent method, ultrasound-assisted synthesis, melt method, microwave method) greatly affects nanosponge size and uniformity. Ultrasound- smaller, uniform nanosponges, eco-friendly. Melt method- solvent-free, but higher polydispersity⁽¹⁵⁾

Drug properties:

The physicochemical nature of the drug (hydrophobicity, molecular weight, stability, pKa) determines its compatibility with nanosponge cavities. Hydrophobic drugs- efficiently trapped in hydrophilic crosslinkers⁽¹⁶⁾

Reaction conditions:

Temperature, pH, and reaction time all modulate nanosponges formation. High temperature accelerates crosslinking but may degrade sensitive drug. Longer reaction time-higher yield but risk of aggregation⁽²⁾

CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES

Characterization of NSs must systematically describe size, morphology, surface chemistry, porosity, crystallinity, thermal behaviour, drug loading, release, and residual/toxic impurities. A combination of physicochemical, spectroscopic, thermal and analytical techniques is therefore required to build a profile suitable for publication and regulatory review. Below are the core techniques and how they are applied to nanosponges.

Particle size & polydispersity – Dynamic light scattering(DLS)/ Photon correlation spectroscopy:

Measures intensity fluctuations of scattered light from particles in suspension to hydrodynamic diameter and polydispersity index(PDI). Average hydrodynamic size(nm), size distribution(PDI) and changes after drug loading or surface modification. Important for predicting biodistribution and cellular uptake. That typical parameter is sample conc low enough to avoid multiple scattering; refractive index of material set measurement at 25°C report Z- average and PDI. Interpretation-Z average less 200-300 nm often desired for systemic delivery; PDI less 0.2 indicates narrow distribution. A large increase after loading indicates aggregation or poor colloidal stability. Representative use DLS is routinely reported in CD-NS Studies⁽²⁾

Surface charge -Zeta potential

Electrophoretic mobility measurement converted to zeta potential; indicates particle surface electrostatics.

Colloidal stability (electrostatic repulsion), likely interactions with cells and proteins (opsonization) and effect of surface modification, (PEGylation, ligands). That typical parameters measure in appropriate buffer and at physiological pH (7.4) REPORT MEAN (Plus/minus)SD. Interpretation greater 25-30 mV generally indicates good electrostatic stabilization near neutral systems rely on steric stabilizers. Representative use zeta reported with DLS across reviews and experimental reports to support colloidal stability claims⁽¹⁾

Morphology & internal structure-scanning & transmission electron microscopy

SEM images surface morphology by scanning with an electron beam ; TEM images internal structure and fine pores by transmission of electrons. Particle shape (spherical, irregular) , surface texture, presence of hollow structures, and distribution of pores or guest material (TEM can show electron-dense drug aggregates). That parameters for SEM coat-conductive sample (Au/Pd) accelerating voltage 5-20kV. For ultrathin sectioning or drop-casting on carbon grids. Stain if needed. Interpretation use SEM to confirm morphology and size trends TEM resolves internal porosity and inclusion of guest molecules. Representative use SEM/TEM used in virtually all experimental nanosponge papers⁽¹⁾

Porosity & surface area -N₂ Adsorption (BET), pore size distribution

Adsorption/desorption isotherms of nitrogen at 77 K; Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method for surface area; Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJK) or NLDFT for pore distribution. Specific surface area (m²/g) total pore volume and pore size distribution (micro/meso/macropores). Critical for relating porosity to drug loading and release. That typical parameters degas samples (e.g., 100-200°C under vacuum) to remove adsorbates; measures full adsorption/desorption cycle. Interpretation high BET favors adsorption capacity but must be combined with pore chemistry (hydrophobic/hydrophilic) to predict host-guest interactions. Mesopores (2-50nm) often enable diffusion-controlled release. Representative use BET analyses are used to compare CD-MOF hybrids and hyper-crosslinked polymer NSs in reviews and experimental reports⁽¹⁾

Crystallinity & phase analysis -Powder X-ray diffraction(PXRD)

X-ray scattering yields diffraction pattern from crystalline domains amorphous materials show broad halos. Degree of crystallinity(loss/retention of native CD crystallinity after crosslinking), presence of crystalline drug(vs amorphously dispersed drug), and structural changes upon loading. That typical parameters scan 2 range 3-60° (depending on sample) compare unloaded NS, pure drug and loaded NS diffractograms. Interpretation disappearance of drug crystalline peaks in loaded NS indicate ordered framework especially for MOF hybrids). Representative use PXRD commonly used to demonstrate drug amorphization upon NS loading⁽⁴⁾

Chemical bonding & functional groups – Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

IR absorbance bands correspond to molecular vibrations(functional groups) evidence of crosslink formation (appearance/disappearance/shifts of C=O, C-O, N-H bands), inclusion complexation (shifts/attenuations of drug peaks), and surface functionalization. That typical parameters FTIR OR KBr pellet, spectral range 4000-400 cm⁻¹ report key peak positions and assignments. Interpretation shifts or suppression of characteristic drug peaks suggest inclusion/interaction: appearance of new bands (carbonate, urethane) confirms linkage chemistry. Representative use FT-IR is foundational in many CD-NS papers to confirm crosslinking chemistry and drug interactions⁽¹⁾

Local chemical environment & confirmation of inclusion -solid-state NMR (13C CP/ MAS, 1H)

Magic-angle spinning(MAS) solid-state NMR Probes local chemical environment of nuclei(13C, 1H), Sensitive to inclusion and crosslinking. Chemical shifts and peak broadening indicate host-guest interactions, presence of specific linkages, and degree of mobility of entrapped drug. That typical parameters 13C CP/MAS at appropriate spinning rates(5-15 kHz); ref TMS. Interpretation new carbonyl signals for carbonate linkages, shift of drug resonances upon inclusion vs physical mixture confirm complexation. Representative use solid-state NMR has been used to

confirm inclusion and crosslink formation in CD-NS⁽¹⁾

Thermal behaviour & stability -Differential scanning calorimetry(DSC) & Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

DSC measures heat flow (endotherms/exotherms) vs temperature (melting, glass transitions); TGA measures mass loss vs temperature(decomposition, solvent loss). Melting point changes and disappearances of drug melting endotherm indicate amorphization/inclusion; TGA shows thermal stability; moisture content, and organic/inorganic loading. That typical parameter heating rates 5-10°C/min under N₂; DSC scan up to 300°C (depending on stability). Interpretation loss of drug melting peak in DSC + absence of PXRD peaks supports amorphous dispersion. TGA residual mass can indicate inorganic fillers or metal content. Representative use: DSC/TGA used in majority of NS studies to document drug amorphization and NS thermal stability⁽⁴⁾

Drug loading, encapsulation efficiency & assay - UV-vis /HPLC/LC-MS

Quantitative determination of drug conc released/dissolved from NS by UV-vis spectrophotometry or chromatographic methods (HPLC/LC-MS). Loading capacity (mg drug per g NS), encapsulation efficiency(% of input drug incorporated), and release kinetics(in vitro release studies). That typical parameters develop validated HPLC method (linearity, LOD/LOQ), use appropriate dissolution media (PBS 7.4, gastric pH 1.2., etc), sample filters(0.22 nanometers) to avoid particulate carryover. Representative use encapsulation metrics and release profiles are central to NS papers⁽¹²⁾

In vitro release & kinetic modelling

Release measured by sampling release medium over time fit to kinetic models to infer mechanisms(diffusion, erosion, swelling), Rate and mechanisms of drug liberation from NS under simulated physiological conditions. That typical parameters use sink conditions, appropriate pH/enzymes if relevant, agitation at 50-100 rpm; sample volumes and replacement ensure sink.

Interpretation fit curves to Higuchi(diffusion), Korsymer-Peppas(mechanisms exponent n) to infer Fickian vs anomalous transport. Representative use standard in NS evaluation papers routinely report kinetics and correlate with crosslink density⁽²⁾

Residual solvent, crosslinkers and metal analysis - GC/MS, HPLC ICP-MS

Analytical chemistry methods for trace residuals: GC/MS for volatile solvents and small organics, HPLC for nonvolatile monomers/by-products, ICP-

MS for metal ions. Safety metrics-presence and quantity of toxic residuals (epichlorohydrin, phenol from DPC). That typical parameter sensitive validated methods with appropriate LOD (ppb-ppm); compare with ICH residual solvent guidelines. Interpretation residuals above acceptable limits necessitate further purification or alternative chemistries. Representative use increasing emphasized in translation papers and regulatory discussions⁽¹⁵⁾

Cyclodextrin-based & Nanosponge as versatile carriers: Methods, Therapeutic intent

Table 7 - Cyclodextrin-based & nanosponge(CD-NS) and related nanosponge for oral topical and related routes, covering method used, intended purpose and reported(2024-2020)

Sr. No	Year	Drug/ model	Method	Route	Purpose/ proposed intention	Report
1	2024	Lumiracoxib (COX-2inhibitor)	β -CD nanospnge (carbonate crosslink, DPC)-Topical Gel	Topical	Improve solubility, skin retention, sustained local release for psoriaticarthritis	Large solubility increase & improved in-vitro metrics ⁽¹⁷⁾
2	2024	Curcumin (topical hydrogel composite)	Cyclodextrin MOF + CD-NS composite-hydrogel	Topical	Increase solubility retention and skin delivery of curcumin	Improved topical delivery vs free curcumin ⁽³⁾
3	2024	Sesamol / photolabile antioxidants	Encapsulation in β -CD nanosponges	Topical	Protect from photodegradation to skin	Improved photostability & encapsulation efficiency ⁽¹⁸⁾
4	2024	Entrectinib (poorly soluble anticancer)	DPC - crosslinked HP- β -CD nanosponge optimization	Oral	Improve dissolution and oral bioavailability	Improved dissolution metrics in formulation study ⁽²⁾
5	2024	Ketoprofen (NSAID topical)	CD-NS loaded into topical hydrogels	Topical	Prolonged release to reduce dosing frequency	Sustained release & elevated skin levels reported ⁽¹⁹⁾
6	2024	Trans-cinnamaldehyde (preservative)	β -CD nanosponge encapsulation	Topical / formulation stability	Improve encapsulation & stability for topical use	High encapsulation efficiency & stability gains ⁽²⁰⁾
7	2024	Colon-targeted anticancer strategies	CD-NS with enteric / colon coatings (reviewed approaches)	Oral (colon targeted)	Protect until colon, local release for colon cancer therapy	Preclinical promising: more translational work needed ⁽²⁰⁾

8	2024	Photostable topical antioxidant composites	CD-NS integrated in hydrogels	Topical	Protect light sensitive actives & release slowly	Improved stability vs free actives ⁽³⁾ .
9	2024	Nano-composite carriers (CD-MOF + CD-NS)	Composite carriers incorporated into hydrogel	Topical	Synergize adsorption & controlled release for skin delivery	Composite outperformed single carriers ⁽³⁾
10	2024	Ketoconazole NS gel	Hypercrosslinked β -CD nanosponge	Topical	Improve antifungal activity & spreadability of gels	Optimized NS gels has good spread ,pH and antifungal effect ⁽²¹⁾
11	2024	Bioavailability enhancers for phytochemicals	CD-NS as bioenhancers of curcumin / resveratrol (review)	Oral	Enhance solubility & systemic exposure of phytochemicals	Reviews conclude CD-NS significance enhance bioavailability in preclinical studies ⁽²²⁾
12	2024	Drug-loaded ns for topical inflammatory conditions	CD-NS in gel formulations	Topical	Sustain release for anti-inflammatory action	In-vitro sustained release & improved retention ⁽²²⁾
13	2024	Various small molecules	Process optimization Soxhlet purification ratio optimization	Oral / topical	Improve reproducibility, yield and encapsulation efficiency	Process studies report improved yields & encapsulation after optimization ⁽²³⁾
14	2024	Study on nanosponge formulation design (review)	DPC, CDI PMDA crosslinkers covered	Oral / topical	Compare crosslinkers and methods for best performance	Review identifies DPC & CDI as common crosslinkers with good results ⁽¹⁾
15	2024	Antioxidant delivery (skin)	CD-NS in hydrogels / creams	Topical	Enhance skin antioxidant delivery & chemical stability	Improved skin delivery and stability metrics ⁽¹⁸⁾
16	2024	Scale-up & regulatory overview	Process & analytical method discussions	-	Evaluate manufacturability tox testing & regulatory readiness	Reviews : strong preclinical data but need standardized scale – up and toxicology work ⁽²⁾

17	2024	Drug combinations in NS for synergistic topical therapy	Dual – drug loading into CD-NS –Gel	Topical	Co-delivery to improve multi mechanism topical therapy	In-vitro co delivery and sustained release achievable ⁽³⁾
18	2024	Anticancer payloads (preclinical)	CD-NS used for hydrophobic anticancer agents	Local / systemic	Improve tumor uptake & control release to reduce side effects	In vitro & small animal studies promising ; clinical translation limited ⁽¹⁾
19	2024	Topical gel optimization studies (ketoconazole)	NS formulation – HPMC/HPMC -gel optimization	Topical	Optimize viscosity spreadability & drug release	Optimized gels had desirable rheology and antifungal action ⁽²¹⁾
20	2024	CD-NS for poorly soluble marketed drugs	DPC / CDI crosslinked CD-NS, drug loading by adsorption	Oral	Reformulation improve oral performance of marketed BCS II drugs	Improved dissolution shown in case studies ⁽¹⁾
21	2023	Resveratrol (oral sustained)	Cyclodextrin-based microspheres/ nanosponge approach	Oral	Increase aqueous solubility and sustain release	Enhanced solubility & sustained release ⁽¹⁸⁾ .
22	2023	Curcumin (amphiphilic CD nanoassemblies)	Amphiphilic cyclodextrin nanoassemblies	Oral / topical	Enhance solubility & cellular uptake	Higher dissolution & cell uptake vs free curcumin ⁽²⁴⁾
23	2023	Multiple anticancer model drugs (reviewed)	CD-NS with stimuli responsive crosslinkers (research)	Local / systemic	Triggered release tumor targeting & reduce systemic toxicity	Promising in vitro animal / clinical evidence limited ⁽¹⁴⁾
24	2023	Griseofulvin (topical/ alternative uses)	Griseofulvin NS formulations tested for topical potential	Topical / oral	Local antifungal delivery & improved retention	In-vitro antifungal activity and retention improved ⁽²⁵⁾
25	2023	Targeted colon delivery	CD-NS with pH sensitive coatings	Oral (colon)	Protect drug until colon for local therapy	Preclinical show potential more in vivo/scale-up data required ⁽²⁵⁾
26	2022	Ketoconazole (Antifungal)	β -CD nanosponges HPMC gel	Topical	Boost solubility permeation sustained antifungal release	Increased permeation & antifungal activity in vitro/ex-vivo
27	2022	Itraconazole (topical)	β -CD + DPC crosslinked NS gel	Topical	Improve solubility skin permeation controlled release	Better solubility and prolonged release ⁽²⁰⁾

28	2022	Multiple phytochemicals (curcumin, quercetin)	CD-NS prepared by DPC/CDI crosslinking (reviewed)	Oral / topical	Improve solubility, stability & bioavailability of phytochemicals	Reviews report consistent improvements ⁽¹⁾
29	2022	Model antifungal API (econazole, others)	CD-NS(DPC crosslink)- gel systems	Topical	Increase solubility & prolong skin contact to boost efficacy	Improved ex-vivo permeation & anti-fungal zones ⁽¹⁹⁾
30	2022	Model lipophilic drugs (review)	NS (polymeric crosslinking) formed by solvent / emulsion methods	Oral	Improve dissolution and oral absorption of lipophilic drugs	Improved dissolution rates in multiple reports ⁽¹⁹⁾
31	2022	Generic small molecules (reviews)	Solvent evaporation melt, emulsion, DPC crosslink methods	Oral / topical	Summarize NS ad solubility enhancers taste masking sustained release	Reviews show consistent preclinical success ⁽¹⁹⁾
32	2022	Curcumin delivery with CD nanoassemblies	Amphiphilic CD nanoassemblies	Oral / topical	Improve solubility and cellular uptake over plain curcumin	Improved dissolution and uptake reported ⁽²⁴⁾
33	2022	General nanosponge performance survey	Review of porous polymeric NS for multiple APIs	Oral / topical	Summarize efficacy of NS across drug classes	NS generally improve solubility, stability and control release ⁽¹⁹⁾
34	2022-24	Method comparative reviews & best practices	Reviews compare melt, solvent, crosslinking & emulsion methods	Oral / topical	Identify best methods for yield porosity and loading for given API	Reviews state method choice depends on API crosslinking (DPC/CDI) ⁽¹⁹⁾
35	2021	Curcumin (Comparison study)	β -CD nanosponge vs β -CD inclusion complex (solvent methods)	Topical/ oral	Improve solubility & photostability	Nanosponge outperformed simple inclusion complex ⁽²⁴⁾
36	2021	curcumin (β -CD-NS)	β -CD nanosponge by DPC , drug loading by solvent diffusion	Oral / topical	Increase solubility and control release	Marked solubility enhancement vs free drug ⁽¹⁶⁾
37	2021-24	Antifungal azoles (fluconazole, ketoconazole)	CD-NS -topical formulations	Topical	Increase solubility prolong contact time for sustained antifungal effect	Ex-vivostudies show enhanced permeation and efficacy ⁽²³⁾ .

38	2021-24	Photostability protection of labile drugs	CD-NS encapsulation stability testing	Topical / oral	Protect drugs from light / heat degradation	Many studies show improved photostability after encapsulation ⁽¹⁶⁾
39	2020	Griseofulvin (pediatric oral liquid)	β -CD nanosponge vs β -CD inclusion complex (solvent methods)	Oral (pediatric)	Taste-masking increase dissolution and oral bioavailability	Taste masking, better dispersion and dissolution ⁽¹⁴⁾
40	2020-24	Pediatric oral liquids (case studies)	β -CD nanosponge dispersions for oral liquid	Oral (paediatric)	Taste masking & improved dispersion for children	Case studies report better palatability & dissolution ⁽¹⁴⁾

APPLICATION OF NANOSPONGES:

The major applications areas for nanosponges especially cyclodextrin based nanosponges and related porous “Nanosponge” materials.

- **Pharmaceutical drug delivery** – oral bioavailability & solubility enhancement

Nanosponges increase apparent solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs, protect labile drugs from degradation and can change pharmacokinetics (improve C_{max}/AUC or provide sustained release. Concrete, reproducible example demonstrating that CD-NSs can convert a BCS-class poor-solubility API into a formulation with markedly improved systemic exposure-useful as a methods + results citation for an oral delivery subsection⁽¹⁾

- **Cancer therapy-targeted & stimulus - responsive delivery**

NSs can carry chemotherapeutics protect them route, increase tumor accumulation (EPR and active targeting) and enable stimuli-responsive release (pH, GSH) for tumor selectivity. Classic demonstration that CD-NS can increase therapeutic index of anthracyclines by improving tumor delivery and lowering off -target toxicity⁽¹⁾

- **Topical, dermal & dermatological therapy (antifungal, wound/healing)**

For skin delivery NS-based gels/hydrogels increase drug retention in stratum corneum, improve

solubility, sustain release, and reduce systemic absorption-attractive for antifungals, anti-inflammatory and active like curcumin. Topical NSs are among the most advanced translational uses (several patents and preclinical studies) because skin formulations tolerate some residuals and NSs provide clear retention/release advantages⁽¹⁾

- **Pulmonary / inhalation delivery (potential & particle engineering strategies)**

Delivering nanoparticle-loaded dry powders to the lung (DPI) requires particle engineering -NSs can be converted inhalable powders (spray-dry/nano-sprays/spray-freeze drying) to delivery poorly soluble actives locally or systemically⁽¹²⁾

- **Environmental remediation and pollutant adsorption (organics, dyes, pesticides, metal)**

CD-NSs bind hydrophobic organic pollutants via inclusions and functionalized NSs with anionic groups can sequester cationic pollutants / heavy metals- application span wastewater treatment, pesticide removal and regeneration of adsorbents. Many studies show very fast adsorption and high removal efficiency⁽¹⁾

- **Catalysis & energy (nanosponges, nanoporous metals)**

Nansponges-types materials (hyper-crosslinked, polymers, nanoporous metal like nanoporous gold) provide very high surface area, accessible active sites and porosity that can boost catalytic rates/selectivity

or be used in electrochemical energy conversion. Catalysis uses a broader definition of NS (both polymeric porous sponges and nanoporous metals).

- **Theranostics & multifunctional (drug +imaging /combined modalities)**

Hybrid NS-MOF or metal-loaded NSs can combine drug delivery with imaging contrast or catalytic activity (e.g., drug + MRI agent or drug + photothermal). Hybridization (MOF, magnetic NPs, metallic dopants) turns NSs into multifunctional agents -promising but raises regulatory and toxicity questions(metal leaching, clearance)⁽³⁾

Emerging trends & advanced designs in nanosponges

“Classical β -cyclodextrin + crosslinkers nanospnge. Advanced deigns aim to overcome limitations like limited drug compatibility, toxicity of some crosslinkers, and lack of targeting. Major emerging trends include:

1. **Stimuli-responsive nanosponges:** NSs modified to release drugs in response to internal stimuli (pH, glutathione, enzymes) or external triggers(light, ultrasound, magnetic fields).
2. **Hybrid / multifunctional nanosponges**
 - **CD-MOF composites:** combine the high surface area of metal-organic frameworks with biocompatibility of CDs
 - **Magnetic nanosponges:** β -CD NSs with magnetic nanoparticles- allow magnetic targeting or easy recovery from wastewater
 - **Metal- loaded “nanosponges”** : nanoporous gold, platinum or palladium NSs catalytic and energy applications⁽³⁾
3. **Surface functionalization for targeting**
 - PEGylation improves blood circulation and reduces immune clearance.
 - **Ligand-Modified NSs** – Antibodies, folic acid or peptides attached for cell specific targeting⁽²⁶⁾

4. Eco-friendly synthesis & green nanosponge

- Replacing toxic solvents(DMF, DMSO) with ethanol/water.
- Using safer crosslinker (citric acid, carbonate-based) instead of toxic diisocyanates.

5. Advanced applications beyond drug delivery

- **Theranostics (therapy + diagnostics):** Hybrid NSs loaded with imaging agents.
- **Catalysis:** Nanoporous inorganic NSs for CO₂ Conversion, oxidation reactions.

CONCLUSION:

Cyclodextrin based nanosponges represent a transformative advancement in nanotechnology-driven drug delivery. Their unique structure provides high drug-loading capacity, improved solubility of poorly water-soluble molecules, and the ability to sustain or target release across multiple routes particularly oral and topical. Evidence from recent studies confirms their potential in improving therapeutic outcomes for antifungal, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory drugs while offering benefits such as taste and masking. Emerging designs, including stimuli-responsive, hybrid and eco-friendly nanosponges further expand their scope in both pharmaceutical and environmental applications. Despite these advantages translation into clinical practice by toxicity concerns, scale-up difficulties and regulatory barriers. Further research should focus on green synthesis, reproducible large scale methods, and comprehensive toxicological evaluation to accelerate clinical acceptance. Overall cyclodextrin-based and advanced nanosponges hold strong promise as multifunctional platforms for next generations oral and topical therapeutics.

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